

Thermodynamic stability of some elementary chemical reactions investigated within the framework of comprehensive thermodynamic theory of stability of irreversible processes (CTTSIP)[†]

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The problem of thermodynamic stability of the process of chemical conversions at finite rates has been investigated using the recently developed comprehensive thermodynamic theory of stability of irreversible processes (CTTSIP). The CTTSIP uses the fabric of Lyapunov's second method (also termed as the direct method) of stability of motion. The excess rate of entropy production in the thermodynamic perturbation space has been defined as the required thermodynamic Lyapunov function, L_s , thereby inheriting the dictates of the second law of thermodynamics. The systems studied as model and presented in this paper are $A \rightarrow X$ and $A \rightleftharpoons X$, and the autocatalytic ones namely $A + X \rightarrow 2X$ and $A + X \rightleftharpoons 2X$ including the process of chemical relaxation in the cases of opposing reactions. The domains of thermodynamic stability under the constantly acting small disturbances, thermodynamic asymptotic stability and thermodynamic instability in these model systems get established.

Introduction

The laws of thermodynamics are followed in all processes that fall within the purview of thermodynamics and the all pervading power of this assertion is reflected by the fact that not a single example has emerged so far to contradict it¹. However, to comprehend the details of how laws of thermodynamics govern the processes of this universe various ways and means have been invented and tested. One such tool is to study the thermodynamic stability of a system. Thus when a system happens to be in equilibrium its stability gets ascertained by the impossibility prescribed by the second law of thermodynamics^{2,3}, namely, a system in equilibrium on its own cannot leave the equilibrium state. However, when it is the case of a nonequilibrium state several difficulties surface out. This is rather a bit of surprise because the celebrated Lyapunov's theory of stability of motion is now more than a century old⁴⁻⁶, the gist of this theory is given in the appendix for the convenience of the reader. Of course, in past, attempts have been made, for example, that of Glansdorff and Prigogine^{7,8} and Stratonovich⁹. Out of these two the former is well documented¹⁰. However, the proponents of these and other theories admit that their theories basically pertain to the so-called local equilibrium regime. Thus there follows an obvious query that for those nonequilibrium states that are not supposed to fall in the domain of the said local equilibrium what should be a valid

description of thermodynamic stability. Therefore, to remove this lacuna, one of us has recently evolved a comprehensive thermodynamic theory of stability of irreversible process (CTTSIP)¹¹⁻¹³ following the fabric of Lyapunov's direct method of stability of motion^{4,5} and Malkin's theorem⁶. CTTSIP defines a thermodynamic Lyapunov function in an appropriate thermodynamic space using the entropy source strength function, which is a positive definite quantity as per the second law of thermodynamics, appearing in Clausius-Duhem inequality^{2,3,14} that reads as

$$\rho \frac{ds}{dt} + \text{div} J_s = \sigma_s \geq 0 \quad (1)$$

where ρ is the mass density, s the per unit mass entropy, J_s the entropy flux density, σ_s the rate of entropy production per unit volume and t the time. The terms involved in eq. (1) are position and time dependent but for the sake of brevity this dependence has not been shown. In CTTSIP the thermodynamic Lyapunov function, L_s , is defined as

$$L_s = |\sigma_s - \sigma_s^0| > 0 \quad (2)$$

where σ_s^0 is the entropy source strength along the real trajectory which is under investigation and σ_s is that along the perturbed one. Further, the coordinates of the perturbation space, $\alpha_1 = |y_1 - y_1^0|$, where y_1 and y_1^0 are the coordinates of the motion along perturbed and real trajectories, respectively,

[†]Dedicated to Professor R. P. Rastogi.

have their differential equation,

$$\frac{d\alpha_i}{dt} = f_i(t, \alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n) \quad (i = 1, 2, \dots, n) \quad (3)$$

and vanish only on the real trajectory. Thus the trivial solution of eq. (3) is

$$\alpha_i \equiv 0 \quad (i = 1, 2, \dots, n) \quad (4)$$

which is the equation of unperturbed motion. Thus by the virtue of the second law of thermodynamics, we have,

$$\sigma_s = \sigma_s(t, \alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n) > 0 \quad (5)$$

$$\alpha_s^0 = \sigma_s(t, 0, 0, \dots, 0) > 0 \quad (6)$$

and correspondingly Lyapunov function, \mathcal{L}_s is expressed as

$$\mathcal{L}_s = \mathcal{L}_s(t, \alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n) > 0 \quad (7)$$

$$\mathcal{L}_s^0 = \mathcal{L}_s(t, 0, 0, \dots, 0) \equiv 0 \quad (8)$$

that is \mathcal{L}_s has a strict minima at the origin. Therefore, from eqs. (7) and (8) it is clear that CTTSIP uses the excess rate of entropy production as the thermodynamic Lyapunov function. Moreover, one of the most important feature of \mathcal{L}_s is that it covers all variety of nonequilibrium situations irrespective of their nature. Now according to Lyapunov's theory of stability of motion^{4,5}, if

$$\frac{d\mathcal{L}_s}{dt} = \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_s}{\partial t} + \sum_i \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_s}{\partial \alpha_i} f_i \leq 0 \quad (9)$$

then the real trajectory which is under scrutiny is stable one. On the other hand, if the left-hand-side rate of eq. (9) behaves as

$$\frac{d\mathcal{L}_s}{dt} \leq -\beta < 0 \quad (10)$$

where β is a positive number and vanishes only for $\alpha_i = 0$ ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$) then the asymptotic stability of motion is guaranteed. In addition to eqs. (2) and (10), if the partial derivatives of \mathcal{L}_s with respect to α_i are all finite then the motion of real trajectory is stable under constantly acting small disturbances in accordance with Malkin's theorem⁶.

For applying above described CTTSIP to a real process one first needs to choose an appropriate thermodynamic space. For chemically reacting spatially uniform systems, the traditional Gibbs relation² is an appropriate one. The traditional Gibbs relation in the time rate form¹⁴ for a spatially uniform closed system undergoing chemical conversions at finite rates reads as^{14,15},

$$\frac{dS}{dt} = T^{-1} \frac{dU}{dt} + pT^{-1} \frac{dV}{dt} - T^{-1} \sum_k \mu_k \frac{dn_k}{dt} \quad (11)$$

where S is the entropy, T the temperature, p the pressure, U the internal energy, V the volume, μ_k the chemical potential per mole of the component k and n_k 's are the mole numbers. Notice that the first two terms on the right-hand-side of eq. (11) are due to the thermal and mechanical interactions and the last term originates due to the occurrence of a chemical reaction at a finite rate. From Dalton's law we have¹⁶,

$$dn_k = \nu_k d\xi \quad (12)$$

where ξ is the extent of advancement of the chemical reaction and ν_k 's are the stoichiometric coefficients taken positive for products and negative for reactants. Further, the standard expression for chemical affinity, A , is¹⁶

$$A = - \sum_k \mu_k \nu_k \quad (13)$$

The substitution of eqs. (12) and (13) into eq. (11) gives

$$\frac{dS}{dt} = T^{-1} \frac{dU}{dt} + pT^{-1} \frac{dV}{dt} + AT^{-1} \frac{d\xi}{dt} \quad (14)$$

We recall that eq. (14) is the De Donderian version of the traditional Gibbs relation in time rate form for spatially uniform closed systems. Thus, in the absence of irreversibility in thermal and mechanical interactions, the entropy source reads as

$$\Sigma_s = \frac{A}{T} \frac{d\xi}{dt} > 0 \quad (15)$$

where

$$\Sigma_s = \frac{d_i S}{dt} = \int_v \sigma_s dV \quad (16)$$

Notice that eq. (15) correctly conforms to the dictates of second law of thermodynamics that is the rate of entropy production is never a negative quantity¹⁷.

In this paper we are presenting our study of the thermodynamic stability within the framework of CTTSIP of two representative elementary chemical reactions. The first case is that of a mechanism in which the reactant in a single step produces a product. The second case is that of autocatalytic mechanism. In both the cases we have investigated the situations in which the reverse reaction on the one hand being not significant and on the other hand being significant. Also the stability of the corresponding chemical relaxation has been investigated. Our presentation, is rather elaborate for the sake of clarity which would help reader to comprehend how the equipment of CTTSIP is to be used.

Representative elementary chemical reactions

Let us consider the following four representative cases of chemical reactions occurring say at constant T and p , namely,

where A is the reactant, X is the product and in autocatalytic mechanism it also acts as a reactant, k_1 and k_2 are the respective rate constants of the chemical reactions depicted in eqs. (17) and (18), k_3 and k_4 are the respective rate constants of the forwards reaction of eqs. (19) and (20), k_{-3} and k_{-4} are the rate constants of the reverse reaction of eqs. (19) and (20). Our analysis of thermodynamic stability of the above chosen chemical reactions presented in the following sections is at constant T and p , which covers various possible situations before and after the effected perturbation.

System not in chemical equilibrium before perturbation

Relevant aspects of stoichiometry and chemical kinetics when mole number of only the reactant is perturbed :

As per the stoichiometry and chemical kinetics¹⁸ we obtain for the rates of consumption and production of reactants and product for the chemical reactions of eqs. (17) – (20) the following relation,

$$\frac{d\xi_i}{dt} = -\frac{dn_A}{dt} = \frac{dn_X}{dt} \quad (i = 1, 2, 3, 4) \quad (21)$$

Thus for the unperturbed case (that is, on the real trajectory) the reaction rates for reactions of eqs. (17) – (20) are given by chemical kinetics as

$$\frac{d\xi_1^0}{dt} = k_1 n_A^0 > 0 \quad (22)$$

$$\frac{d\xi_2^0}{dt} = k_1 n_A^0 n_X^0 > 0 \quad (23)$$

$$\frac{d\xi_3^0}{dt} = k_3 n_A^0 - k_{-3} n_X^0 > 0 \quad (24)$$

$$\frac{d\xi_4^0}{dt} = k_4 n_A^0 n_X^0 - k_{-4} (n_X^0)^2 > 0 \quad (25)$$

where superscript (0) indicates the quantities on the unperturbed trajectory and the subscripts to ξ match with that for the respective forward rate constants. The positive definiteness of eqs. (22) – (25) asserts that we are considering in particular those cases and the stages of reaction where the overall reaction proceeds in the forward direction. Now let us consider the case when only the concentration of A is perturbed by a sufficiently small amount say, δn_A , we then have,

$$d\xi = |\xi - \xi^0| > 0, \quad \delta n_A = |n_A - n_A^0| > 0 \quad (26)$$

On the perturbed trajectory, we have,

$$\frac{d\xi_1}{dt} = k_1 n_A > 0 \quad (27)$$

$$\frac{d\xi_2}{dt} = k_2 n_A n_X^0 > 0 \quad (28)$$

$$\frac{d\xi_3}{dt} = k_3 n_A - k_{-3} n_X^0 > 0 \quad (29)$$

$$\frac{d\xi_4}{dt} = k_4 n_A n_X^0 - k_{-4} (n_X^0)^2 > 0 \quad (30)$$

As δn_A by definition is sufficiently small the positive rates of eqs. (22) – (25) are still retained on the perturbed trajectory as shown in eqs. (27) – (30).

Now on subtracting eqs. (22) and (24) respectively from eqs. (27) and (29), we obtain,

$$\frac{d\xi}{dt} - \frac{d\xi^0}{dt} = \frac{d(\xi - \xi^0)}{dt} = -\frac{d(n_A - n_A^0)}{dt} = k(n_A - n_A^0) \quad (31)$$

and similarly from eqs. (23), (25), (28) and (30) we obtain,

$$\frac{d\xi}{dt} - \frac{d\xi^0}{dt} = \frac{d(\xi - \xi^0)}{dt} = -\frac{d(n_A - n_A^0)}{dt} = k n_X^0 (n_A - n_A^0) \quad (32)$$

as the stoichiometry prescribes that,

$$-dn_A = d\xi, \quad -dn_A^0 = d\xi^0 \quad (33)$$

Notice that we have dropped the subscripts to rate constant and ξ as the form of the right-hand-side expression for $d(\xi - \xi^0)/dt$ obtained in the above four cases are, $k_1(n_A - n_A^0)$, $k_2 n_X^0 (n_A - n_A^0)$, $k_3(n_A - n_A^0)$, and $k_4 n_X^0 (n_A - n_A^0)$. The same practice will be adhered with in all the cases considered in this paper with only a few exceptions wherever the clarity

of the presentation demands.

Thus we have from eq. (31),

$$\frac{d|n_A - n_A^0|}{dt} = \frac{d(\delta n_A)}{dt} = -k\delta n_A \leq -\beta < 0 \quad (34)$$

$$\left| \frac{d(\xi - \xi^0)}{dt} \right| = k\delta n_A \geq \beta > 0 \quad (35)$$

and from eq. (32) we have,

$$\frac{d|n_A - n_A^0|}{dt} = \frac{d(\delta n_A)}{dt} = -kn_X^0 \delta n_A \leq -\beta < 0 \quad (36)$$

$$\left| \frac{d(\xi - \xi^0)}{dt} \right| = kn_X^0 \delta n_A \geq \beta > 0 \quad (37)$$

where β is a positive number and vanishes only at the origin, that is, on the unperturbed trajectory. Also we do have,

$$\frac{\partial n_X^0}{\partial \xi} = \frac{dn_X^0}{d\xi}, \quad \frac{\partial \xi^0}{\partial \xi} = \frac{\partial \xi^0}{\partial \xi}, \quad \text{etc.} \quad (38)$$

as on the real trajectory by definition we have $(n_A - n_A^0) = 0 = (\xi - \xi^0)$.

On assuming the reaction mixture as an ideal gas mixture, the chemical affinity is given by thermodynamics on unperturbed trajectory as

$$A_i^0 = A_i^\theta + RT \ln \left(\frac{n_A^0}{n_X^0} \right) \quad (i = 1, 2, 3, 4) \quad (39)$$

where A_i^0 is the chemical affinity on the unperturbed trajectory, A_i^θ the chemical affinity in standard reference state, and R the gas constant. As the concentration of only A is perturbed by a sufficiently small amount, δn_A , hence chemical affinity on perturbed trajectory in all the above four cases reads as

$$A = A^0 + RT \ln \left(1 \pm \frac{\delta n_A}{n_A^0} \right) \quad (40)$$

However, by definition we have $\delta n_A \ll n_A^0$ the logarithmic term of eq. (40) approximates to zero and hence for all practical purposes, we have

$$A_i \approx A_i^\theta + RT \ln \left(\frac{n_A^0}{n_X^0} \right) = A_i^0 \quad (41)$$

The local time derivative in thermodynamic perturbation space of eq. (39) is obtained as

$$\frac{\partial (A_i^0 / T)}{\partial \xi} = -R \left[\frac{1}{n_A^0} + \frac{1}{n_X^0} \right] \frac{\partial (n_X^0)_i}{\partial \xi} < 0 \quad (42)$$

wherein the dictates of stoichiometry of the reactions have been incorporated. Now we are equipped with the necessary expressions based on chemical kinetics and thermodynamics for the purpose of investigating the thermodynamic stability of the considered chemical reactions using the CTTSIP framework.

Thermodynamic stability : With the notation adopted in CTTSIP the rate of entropy production on the perturbed trajectory in the present cases is given by eq. (15) but in view of eq. (41) it specifically reads as

$$\Sigma_s = \frac{A^0}{T} \frac{d\xi}{dt} > 0 \quad (43)$$

and that on the unperturbed trajectory it would read as

$$\Sigma_s^0 = \frac{A^0}{T} \frac{d\xi^0}{dt} > 0 \quad (44)$$

Now in the present case the thermodynamic Lyapunov function, \mathcal{L}_s , gets the following expression,

$$\mathcal{L}_s = |\Sigma_s - \Sigma_s^0| > 0 \quad (45)$$

Next on combining eqs. (43) and (44) with eq. (45), we obtain,

$$\mathcal{L}_s = \left| \frac{A^0}{T} \frac{d\xi}{dt} - \frac{A^0}{T} \frac{d\xi^0}{dt} \right| > 0 \quad (46)$$

which, on using eq. (35) and in view of A^0/T being a positive quantity, further simplifies to

$$\mathcal{L}_s = \frac{A^0}{T} \left| \frac{d(\xi - \xi^0)}{dt} \right| = k \frac{A^0}{T} \delta n_A \geq \beta' > 0 \quad (47)$$

and on using eq. (37) it produces,

$$\mathcal{L}_s = \frac{A^0}{T} \left| \frac{d(\xi - \xi^0)}{dt} \right| = k \frac{A^0}{T} n_X^0 \delta n_A \geq \beta' > 0 \quad (48)$$

where β' is a positive number and vanishes only on the real trajectory. Thus we have,

$$\mathcal{L}_s = \mathcal{L}_s(t, \delta n_A) \quad (49)$$

The total time derivative of \mathcal{L}_s is obtained as

$$\frac{d\mathcal{L}_s}{dt} = \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_s}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_s}{\partial (\delta n_A)} \frac{d(\delta n_A)}{dt} \quad (50)$$

The local time derivative of \mathcal{L}_s in thermodynamic perturbation space is obtained from eq. (47) ,

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_s}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial(A^0/T)}{\partial t} k \delta n_A \quad (51)$$

and that from eq.(48) as

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_s}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial(A^0/T)}{\partial t} k n_X^0 \delta n_A + \frac{A^0}{T} k \delta n_A \frac{\partial n_X^0}{\partial t} \quad (52)$$

On incorporating eq. (42) into eq. (51), we obtain,

$$\frac{\partial (\mathcal{L}_s)_i}{\partial t} = -R \left(\frac{1}{n_A^0} + \frac{1}{n_X^0} \right) \frac{\partial (n_X^0)_i}{\partial t} k \delta n_A < 0 \quad (i = 1, 3) \quad (53)$$

and from eqs. (42) and (52) we have,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial (\mathcal{L}_s)_i}{\partial t} = & -R \left(\frac{1}{n_A^0} + \frac{1}{n_X^0} \right) \frac{\partial (n_X^0)_i}{\partial t} k n_X^0 \delta n_A \\ & + \frac{A^0}{T} k \delta n_A \frac{\partial (n_X^0)_i}{\partial t} \quad \begin{matrix} > 0 \\ < 0 \end{matrix} (i = 2, 4) \end{aligned} \quad (54)$$

whereas the gradients of \mathcal{L}_s in two cases are obtained as

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_s}{\partial (\delta n_A)} = \frac{A^0}{T} \frac{\partial}{\partial (\delta n_A)} (k \delta n_A) = \frac{A^0}{T} k > 0 \text{ and finite} \quad (55)$$

and

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_s}{\partial (\delta n_A)} = \frac{A^0}{T} \frac{\partial}{\partial (\delta n_A)} (k n_X^0 \delta n_A) = \frac{A^0}{T} k n_X^0 > 0 \text{ and finite} \quad (56)$$

Thus on combining eqs. (34) and (36) respectively with eqs. (55) and (56) yield,

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_s}{\partial (\delta n_A)} = \frac{d(\delta n_A)}{dt} = -\frac{A^0}{T} k^2 \delta n_A < 0 \quad (57)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_s}{\partial (\delta n_A)} \frac{d(\delta n_A)}{dt} = -\frac{A^0}{T} k^2 (n_X^0)^2 \delta n_A < 0 \quad (58)$$

Now on substitution of eqs. (53) and (57) into eq. (50), we obtain,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial (\mathcal{L}_s)_i}{\partial t} = & -kR \left(\frac{1}{n_A^0} + \frac{1}{n_X^0} \right) \delta n_A \frac{\partial (n_X^0)_i}{\partial t} \\ & - \frac{A^0}{T} k^2 \delta n_A \leq -\beta'' < 0 \end{aligned} \quad (59)$$

whereas from eqs. (50), (54) and (58), we obtain,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial (\mathcal{L}_s)_i}{\partial t} = & -k \left[n_X^0 R \left(\frac{1}{n_A^0} + \frac{1}{n_X^0} \right) - \frac{A^0}{T} \right] \delta n_A \frac{\partial (n_X^0)_i}{\partial t} \\ & - \frac{A^0}{T} k^2 (n_X^0)^2 \delta n_A \quad \begin{matrix} > 0 \\ < 0 \end{matrix} \end{aligned} \quad (60)$$

Thus eq. (59) establishes that chemical reactions of eqs. (17) and (19) when proceed at finite rates are asymptotically stable (*cf.* eq. 10). Further, in view of the gradient of \mathcal{L}_s being finite as per eq. (55), this process is also stable under constantly acting small disturbances as per Malkin's theorem⁶. Whereas in the case of autocatalytic reactions of eqs. (18) and (20), the asymptotic stability and the stability under constantly acting small disturbances are guaranteed, as revealed by eq. (60), only when,

$$n_X^0 R \left(\frac{1}{n_A^0} + \frac{1}{n_X^0} \right) > \frac{A^0}{T} \quad (61)$$

This then means that either A must be fed into the reactor at such a rate that during the course of entire autocatalytic chemical conversion there remains $n_X^0 \gg n_A^0$ or X is continuously removed from the reactor such that $n_A^0 \gg n_X^0$ is maintained. In the latter choice one needs to have $A^0 < RT$.

Thermodynamic stability when mole number of only the autocatalytic species is perturbed :

This subsection as per its title, deals only with the chemical reactions of eqs. (18) and (20). In this case the relevant expressions for perturbation are

$$\delta \xi = |\xi - \xi^0| > 0, \quad \delta n_X = |n_X - n_X^0| > 0 \quad (62)$$

Correspondingly, the rates of reaction on the perturbed trajectory read as

$$\frac{d\xi_2}{dt} = k_2 n_A^0 n_X > 0 \quad (63)$$

$$\frac{d\xi_4}{dt} = k_4 n_A^0 n_X - k_{-4} (n_X^0)^2 > 0 \quad (64)$$

The rate of change of perturbation in all these cases is then given by

$$\frac{d\xi_2}{dt} - \frac{d\xi_2^0}{dt} = \frac{d(\xi_2 - \xi_2^0)}{dt} = \quad (65)$$

$$\frac{d(n_X - n_X^0)}{dt} = \pm k_2 n_A^0 \delta n_X$$

$$\frac{d\xi_4}{dt} - \frac{d\xi_4^0}{dt} = \frac{d(\xi_4 - \xi_4^0)}{dt} = \quad (66)$$

$$\frac{d(n_X - n_X^0)}{dt} \approx \pm (k_4 n_A^0 - 2k_{-4} n_X^0) \delta n_X$$

Therefore, from eq. (65), we obtain,

$$\frac{d|n_X - n_X^0|}{dt} = \frac{d\delta n_X}{dt} = k_2 n_A^0 \delta n_X \geq \beta > 0 \quad (67)$$

$$\left| \frac{d(\xi - \xi^0)}{dt} \right| = k_2 n_A^0 \delta n_X \geq \beta > 0 \quad (68)$$

and from eq. (66) there result,

$$\frac{d|n_X - n_X^0|}{dt} = \frac{d\delta n_X}{dt} = (k_4 n_A^0 - 2k_{-4} n_X^0) \delta n_X \begin{matrix} > 0 \\ < 0 \end{matrix} \quad (69)$$

$$\left| \frac{d(\xi - \xi^0)}{dt} \right| = |k_4 n_A^0 - 2k_{-4} n_X^0| \delta n_X \geq \beta > 0 \quad (70)$$

as the rate of change of perturbation in all these cases.

The chemical affinity on the perturbed trajectory reads as

$$A = A^0 - RT \ln \left(1 \pm \frac{dn_X}{n_X^0} \right) \approx A^0 \quad (71)$$

On substitution of eq. (68) into eq. (47), the expression for \mathcal{L}_s is obtained as

$$\mathcal{L}_s = \frac{A^0}{T} \left| \frac{d(\xi - \xi^0)}{dt} \right| = \frac{A^0}{T} k_2 n_A^0 \delta n_X \geq \beta' > 0 \quad (72)$$

and from eqs. (70) and (47), we obtain,

$$\mathcal{L}_s = \frac{A^0}{T} \left| \frac{d(\xi - \xi^0)}{dt} \right| = \frac{A^0}{T} |k_4 n_A^0 - 2k_{-4} n_X^0| \delta n_X \geq \beta' > 0 \quad (73)$$

and hence we have,

$$\mathcal{L}_s = \mathcal{L}_s(t, \delta n_X) \quad (74)$$

The total time derivative of \mathcal{L}_s in this case reads as

$$\frac{d\mathcal{L}_s}{dt} = \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_s}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_s}{\partial (\delta n_X)} \frac{d(\delta n_X)}{dt} \quad (75)$$

The local time derivatives of \mathcal{L}_s in the thermodynamic perturbation space keeping δn_X constant and using eqs. (42) and (72) reads as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_s}{\partial t} &= \frac{\partial (A^0/T)}{\partial t} k_2 n_A^0 \delta n_X \\ &= -k_2 R n_A^0 \delta n_X \left(\frac{1}{n_A^0} + \frac{1}{n_X^0} \right) \frac{\partial n_X^0}{\partial t} < 0 \end{aligned} \quad (76)$$

which vanishes only at the origin, and on using eqs. (42) and (73), we obtain,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_s}{\partial t} &= -R |k_4 n_A^0 - 2k_{-4} n_X^0| \delta n_X \left(\frac{1}{n_A^0} + \frac{1}{n_X^0} \right) \frac{\partial n_X^0}{\partial t} \\ &+ \frac{A^0}{T} \delta n_X \frac{\partial}{\partial t} |k_4 n_A^0 - 2k_{-4} n_X^0| > 0 \end{aligned} \quad (77)$$

which too vanishes only at the origin.

The gradient of \mathcal{L}_s in thermodynamic perturbation space corresponding to eq. (72) is given as

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_s}{\partial (\delta n_X)} = \frac{A^0}{T} k_2 n_A^0 > 0 \text{ and finite} \quad (78)$$

and hence from eqs. (67) and (78), we have,

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_s}{\partial (\delta n_X)} \frac{d(\delta n_X)}{dt} = \frac{A^0}{T} (k_2)^2 (n_A^0)^2 \delta n_X > 0 \quad (79)$$

Similarly, from eqs. (69) and (73), we obtain,

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_s}{\partial (\delta n_X)} = \frac{A^0}{T} |k_4 n_A^0 - 2k_{-4} n_X^0| > 0 > 0 \text{ and finite} \quad (80)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_s}{\partial (\delta n_X)} \frac{d(\delta n_X)}{dt} = \frac{A^0}{T} |k_4 n_A^0 - 2k_{-4} n_X^0|$$

$$(k_4 n_A^0 - 2k_{-4} n_X^0) \delta n_X \begin{matrix} > 0 \\ < 0 \end{matrix} \quad (81)$$

(i) Thus for the autocatalytic chemical reaction of eq. (18), the above expressions, namely, eqs. (76), (78) and (79) reveal that it remains asymptotically stable and also stable under the constantly acting small disturbances only when,

$$R \left(\frac{1}{n_A^0} + \frac{1}{n_X^0} \right) \frac{\partial n_X^0}{\partial t} > k_2 n_X^0 \left(\frac{A^0}{T} \right) \quad (82)$$

as under this condition for \mathcal{L}_s it is guaranteed that,

$$\frac{d\mathcal{L}_s}{dt} \leq -\beta < 0 \quad (83)$$

Notice that eq. (82) gives eq. (61) on substituting the ex-

pression of $\partial n_X^0/\partial t$. Therefore, the same conclusions follow as that has been spelled out below eq. (61) of this paper.

(ii) On the other hand, in the case of autocatalytic chemical reaction of eq. (20) as there is a net production of X, eq. (25) gives,

$$k_4 n_A^0 > k_{-4} n_X^0 \quad (84)$$

but to have the asymptotic stability and the stability under the constantly acting small disturbances according to eqs. (69), (77), (80) and (81), the following conditions must be obeyed, namely,

$$k_4 n_A^0 < 2k_{-4} n_X^0 \quad (85)$$

$$\left[Rn_X^0 \left(\frac{1}{n_A^0} + \frac{1}{n_X^0} \right) - \frac{A^0}{T} \right] > \frac{A^0}{(k_4 n_A^0 - k_{-4} n_X^0) + \frac{A^0}{T} k_{-4} n_X^0} \quad (86)$$

$$> \frac{A^0}{T} \frac{\partial}{\partial T} (\ln |k_4 n_A^0 - 2k_{-4} n_X^0|)$$

Thus the advice that emerges from the present analysis is that either there should not be a significant reverse reaction in the chemical reaction that proceeds by an autocatalytic mechanism or if it cannot be avoided then perturbations in the mole number of the self-catalyst product X should be strictly avoided and the process be carried out under the condition of eq. (61).

With the above revelation there is no point in considering simultaneous perturbation of the mole numbers of A and X.

System in chemical equilibrium before perturbation

The representative examples suitable for consideration in this category from eqs. (17)–(20) are the ones given in eqs. (19) and (20). Herein too we investigate various possibilities on the lines of those situations discussed in the preceding section. As the state of equilibrium corresponds to no entropy production, $\Sigma_s^0 = 0$, the thermodynamic Lyapunov function is obtained as $\mathcal{L}_s = |\Sigma_s|$. But by the second law of thermodynamics, we have $\Sigma_s > 0$ and hence it is convenient to use Σ_s itself as \mathcal{L}_s , that is,

$$\mathcal{L}_s = \Sigma_s = \frac{A}{T} \frac{d\xi}{dt} = \frac{A}{T} \frac{d(\xi - \xi^0)}{dt} > 0 \quad (87)$$

Herein we have utilized the fact that at equilibrium we have $d\xi^0/dt = 0$. Notice that the dictates of eq. (87) are

$$\frac{A}{T} > 0 \rightarrow \frac{d\xi}{dt} > 0, \frac{d(\xi - \xi^0)}{dt} > 0 \quad (88)$$

$$\frac{A}{T} < 0 \rightarrow \frac{d\xi}{dt} < 0, \frac{d(\xi - \xi^0)}{dt} < 0 \quad (89)$$

The case of eq. (88) corresponds to those perturbations in which there is a positive perturbation in the mole numbers of reactants and/or negative perturbation in the mole numbers of products. Whereas the negative perturbation of mole numbers of reactants and/or the positive perturbation of the mole numbers of products correspond to eq. (89). Moreover, at equilibrium we have for reactions of eqs. (19) and (20) the following identities, namely,

$$\frac{d\xi_3^0}{dt} = k_3 n_A^0 - k_{-3} n_X^0 = 0 \rightarrow k_3 n_A^0 = k_{-3} n_X^0 \quad (90)$$

$$\frac{d\xi_4^0}{dt} = k_4 n_A^0 n_X^0 - k_{-4} (n_X^0)^2 = 0 \rightarrow k_4 n_A^0 = k_{-4} n_X^0 \quad (91)$$

The case of nonautocatalytic reaction :

The chemical reaction considered herein is that of eq. (19).

Positive perturbation in the mole number of the reactant : Let the mole number of A is perturbed, this then gives,

$$\frac{d(\xi - \xi^0)}{dt} = k_3 \delta n_A \geq \beta > 0 \quad (92)$$

$$\frac{d(n_A - n_A^0)}{dt} = -k_3 (n_A - n_A^0) \quad (93)$$

$$\frac{d(\delta n_A)}{dt} = -k_3 \delta n_A \leq \beta < 0 \quad (94)$$

The chemical affinity on the perturbed trajectory and hence in the thermodynamic perturbation space (as in equilibrium we have $A^0 = 0$) reads as

$$A = RT \ln \left(1 + \frac{\delta n_A}{n_A^0} \right) > 0 \quad (95)$$

Notice that if $\delta n_A/n_A^0$ can be ignored compared to 1 (as we could do in the case of perturbation of chemical reactions at finite rates) the chemical affinity would be obtained as equal to zero but then it will not amount to an observable perturbation leading to a finite rate of the process after perturbation. Therefore, relatively larger perturbations are required to have a real perturbation of an equilibrium state. Thus one needs to understand in this light what is meant by the sufficiently small perturbation in the Lyapunov theory. Therefore, on using eqs. (92) and (95), the thermodynamic Lyapunov function, \mathcal{L}_s , reads as

$$\mathcal{L}_s = \frac{A}{T} k_3 \delta n_A \geq \beta > 0 \quad (96)$$

The local time derivative of \mathcal{L}_s in thermodynamic perturbation space is obtained as

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_s}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (97)$$

because this time derivative is to be computed keeping δn_A constant. The gradient of \mathcal{L}_s in the thermodynamic perturbation space is obtained as

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_s}{\partial (\delta n_A)} = k_3 \left(R \frac{\delta n_A}{n_A^0 + \delta n_A} + \frac{A}{T} \right) > 0 \text{ and finite} \quad (98)$$

and hence we have,

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_s}{\partial (\delta n_A)} \frac{d(\delta n_A)}{dt} = -(k_3)^2 \left(R \frac{\delta n_A}{n_A^0 + \delta n_A} + \frac{A}{T} \right) \delta n_A < 0 \quad (99)$$

Therefore, the total time derivative reads as

$$\frac{d\mathcal{L}_s}{dt} = -(k_3)^2 \left(R \frac{\delta n_A}{n_A^0 + \delta n_A} + \frac{A}{T} \right) \delta n_A \leq -\beta'' < 0 \quad (100)$$

Thus the conclusion is that the chemical equilibrium is asymptotically stable and in view of the finiteness of the gradient, eq. (98), it is also stable under constantly acting small disturbances.

Negative perturbation in the mole number of the reactant : In this case after the said perturbation the chemical reaction proceeds in the reverse direction, the relevant expressions are

$$\frac{d(\xi - \xi^0)}{dt} = -k_3 \delta n_A \leq -\beta < 0 \quad (101)$$

$$\frac{d(n_A - n_A^0)}{dt} = -k_3(n_A - n_A^0) \quad (102)$$

$$\frac{d(\delta n_A)}{dt} = -k_3 \delta n_A \leq -\beta < 0 \quad (103)$$

$$A = RT \ln \left(1 - \frac{\delta n_A}{n_A^0} \right) < 0 \quad (104)$$

$$\mathcal{L}_s = -\frac{A}{T} k_3 \delta n_A \geq \beta > 0 \quad (105)$$

The magnitude of δn_A is required to be obviously sufficiently small but relatively large enough to initiate a finite rate of the process.

As in the preceding subsection herein too we have $\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_s}{\partial t} = 0$. The gradient of \mathcal{L}_s is obtained as

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_s}{\partial (\delta n_A)} = k_3 \left(R \frac{\delta n_A}{n_A^0 - \delta n_A} - \frac{A}{T} \right) > 0 \text{ and finite} \quad (106)$$

and hence we have,

$$\frac{d\mathcal{L}_s}{dt} = \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_s}{\partial (\delta n_A)} \frac{d(\delta n_A)}{dt} = (k_3)^2 \left(R \frac{\delta n_A}{n_A^0 - \delta n_A} - \frac{A}{T} \right) \delta n_A \leq -\beta' < 0 \quad (107)$$

Thus the asymptotic stability and stability under the constantly acting small disturbances are both guaranteed.

The positive perturbation in mole number of the product : For the chemical reaction of eq. (19) with positive perturbation in the mole number of X the reaction proceeds in the reverse direction and hence we obtain the following expression,

$$\frac{d(n_X - n_X^0)}{dt} = \frac{d(\delta n_X)}{dt} = \frac{d(\xi - \xi^0)}{dt} = -k_{-3} \delta n_X \leq -\beta < 0 \quad (108)$$

$$A = -RT \ln \left(1 + \frac{\delta n_X}{n_X^0} \right) > 0 \quad (109)$$

$$\mathcal{L}_s = -\frac{A}{T} k_{-3} \delta n_X \geq \beta > 0 \quad (110)$$

Herein too we have $\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_s}{\partial t} = 0$. The gradient of \mathcal{L}_s is obtained as

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_s}{\partial (\delta n_X)} = k_{-3} \left(R \frac{\delta n_X}{n_X^0 + \delta n_X} - \frac{A}{T} \right) > 0 \text{ and finite} \quad (111)$$

Therefore, the total time derivative of \mathcal{L}_s is given by,

$$\frac{d\mathcal{L}_s}{dt} = \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_s}{\partial (\delta n_X)} \frac{d(\delta n_X)}{dt} = -(k_{-3})^2 \left(R \frac{\delta n_X}{n_X^0 + \delta n_X} - \frac{A}{T} \right) \delta n_X \leq -\beta' < 0 \quad (112)$$

Thus the asymptotic stability and stability under the constantly acting small disturbances get established.

The negative perturbation in the mole number of product : For the chemical reaction of eq. (19) with negative perturbation in the mole number of X the reaction proceeds in the forward direction and hence we obtain the following expression,

$$\frac{d(n_X - n_X^0)}{dt} = k_{-3} \delta n_X > 0, \quad \frac{d(\delta n_X)}{dt} = -k_{-3} \delta n_X \leq -\beta < 0 \quad (113)$$

$$A = -RT \ln \left(1 - \frac{\delta n_X}{n_X^0} \right) > 0 \quad (114)$$

$$\mathcal{L}_s = \frac{A}{T} k_{-3} \delta n_X \geq \beta > 0 \quad (115)$$

Herein too we have $\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_s}{\partial A} = 0$. The gradient of \mathcal{L}_s is obtained as

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_s}{\partial (\delta n_X)} = k_{-3} \left(R \frac{\delta n_X}{n_X^0 - \delta n_X} + \frac{A}{T} \right) > 0 \text{ and finite} \quad (116)$$

Therefore, the total time derivative of \mathcal{L}_s is given by,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d\mathcal{L}_s}{dt} &= \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_s}{\partial (\delta n_X)} \frac{d(\delta n_X)}{dt} = -(k_{-3})^2 \\ &\left(R \frac{\delta n_X}{n_X^0 - \delta n_X} + \frac{A}{T} \right) \delta n_X \leq -\beta' < 0 \end{aligned} \quad (117)$$

Again it guarantees the asymptotic stability and the stability under constantly acting small disturbances.

The case of autocatalytic reaction :

In this subsection, we consider the chemical reaction of eq. (20) for which we have the following.

Positive perturbation in the mole number of the reactant : Let the mole number of A is perturbed, this then gives,

$$\frac{d(\xi - \xi^0)}{dt} = k_4 n_X^0 \delta n_A \geq \beta > 0 \quad (118)$$

$$\frac{d(n_A - n_A^0)}{dt} = -k_4 (n_A - n_A^0) n_X^0 \quad (119)$$

$$\frac{d(\delta n_A)}{dt} = -k_4 n_X^0 \delta n_A \quad -\beta < 0 \quad (120)$$

The chemical affinity on the perturbed trajectory and hence in the thermodynamic perturbation space (as in equilibrium we have $A^0 = 0$) is given by eq. (95). Hence, the thermodynamic Lyapunov function, \mathcal{L}_s , reads as

$$\mathcal{L}_s = \frac{A}{T} k_4 n_X^0 \delta n_A \geq \beta > 0 \quad (121)$$

The local time derivative of \mathcal{L}_s in thermodynamic perturba-

tion space vanishes as it has to be computed at constant δn_A and n_X^0 is time-independent.

The gradient of \mathcal{L}_s in the thermodynamic perturbation space is obtained as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_s}{\partial (\delta n_A)} &= k_4 n_X^0 \left(R \frac{\delta n_A}{n_A^0 + \delta n_A} + \frac{A}{T} \right) > 0 \\ &\text{and finite} \end{aligned} \quad (122)$$

and hence we have,

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_s}{\partial (\delta n_A)} \frac{d(\delta n_A)}{dt} = -(k_4 n_X^0)^2 \left(R \frac{\delta n_A}{n_A^0 + \delta n_A} + \frac{A}{T} \right) \delta n_A < 0 \quad (123)$$

Therefore, the total time derivative reads as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d\mathcal{L}_s}{dt} &= -(k_4 n_X^0)^2 \left(R \frac{\delta n_A}{n_A^0 + \delta n_A} + \frac{A}{T} \right) \\ &\delta n_A \leq -\beta' < 0 \end{aligned} \quad (124)$$

Thus the conclusion is that the chemical equilibrium is asymptotically stable and in view of the finiteness of the gradient, eq. (122), it is also stable under constantly acting small disturbances.

Negative perturbation in the mole number of the reactant : In this case after the said perturbation the chemical reaction proceeds in the reverse direction, the relevant expressions are

$$\frac{d(\xi - \xi^0)}{dt} = -k_4 n_X^0 \delta n_A \leq -\beta < 0 \quad (125)$$

$$\frac{d(n_A - n_A^0)}{dt} = -k_4 n_X^0 (n_A - n_A^0) \quad (126)$$

$$\frac{d(\delta n_A)}{dt} = -k_4 n_X^0 \delta n_A \leq -\beta < 0 \quad (127)$$

$$A = RT \ln \left(1 - \frac{\delta n_A}{n_A^0} \right) < 0 \quad (128)$$

$$\mathcal{L}_s = -\frac{A}{T} k_4 n_X^0 \delta n_A \geq \beta > 0 \quad (129)$$

The magnitude of δn_A is required to be obviously sufficiently small but relatively large enough to initiate a finite rate of the process.

As in the preceding subsection herein too we have $\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_s}{\partial A} = 0$. The gradient of \mathcal{L}_s is obtained as

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_s}{\partial \delta n_A} = k_4 n_X^0 \left(R \frac{\delta n_A}{n_A^0 - \delta n_A} - \frac{A}{T} \right) > 0 \text{ and finite} \quad (130)$$

and hence we have,

$$\frac{d\mathcal{L}_s}{dt} = \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_s}{\partial \delta n_A} \frac{d(\delta n_A)}{dt} = -(k_4 n_X^0)^2 \left(R \frac{\delta n_A}{n_A^0 - \delta n_A} - \frac{A}{T} \right) \delta n_A \leq -\beta' < 0 \quad (131)$$

That is the asymptotic stability and stability under the constantly acting small disturbances are both guaranteed.

The positive perturbation in mole number of the autocatalytic species : For the chemical reaction of eq. (20) with positive perturbation in the mole number of X the reaction proceeds in the reverse direction and hence we obtain the following expression,

$$\frac{d(n_X - n_X^0)}{dt} = \frac{d(\delta n_X)}{dt} = \frac{d(\xi - \xi^0)}{dt} = k_{-4} n_X^0 \delta n_X \leq -\beta < 0 \quad (132)$$

$$A = -RT \ln \left(1 + \frac{\delta n_X}{n_X^0} \right) < 0 \quad (133)$$

$$\mathcal{L}_s = -\frac{A}{T} k_{-4} n_X^0 \delta n_X \geq \beta > 0 \quad (134)$$

Herein too we have $\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_s}{\partial A} = 0$. The gradient of \mathcal{L}_s is obtained as

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_s}{\partial \delta n_X} = k_{-4} n_X^0 \left(R \frac{\delta n_X}{n_X^0 + \delta n_X} - \frac{A}{T} \right) > 0 \text{ and finite} \quad (135)$$

Therefore, the total time derivative of \mathcal{L}_s is given by,

$$\frac{d\mathcal{L}_s}{dt} = \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_s}{\partial \delta n_X} \frac{d(\delta n_X)}{dt} = -(k_{-4} n_X^0)^2 \left(R \frac{\delta n_X}{n_X^0 + \delta n_X} - \frac{A}{T} \right) \delta n_X \leq -\beta' < 0 \quad (136)$$

Thus the asymptotic stability and stability under the constantly acting small disturbances get established.

The negative perturbation in the mole number of the autocatalytic species : For the chemical reaction of eq. (20) with negative perturbation in the mole number of X the re-

action proceeds in the forward direction and hence we obtain the following expression,

$$\frac{d(n_X - n_X^0)}{dt} = k_{-4} n_X^0 > 0, \quad \frac{d(\delta n_X)}{dt} = k_{-4} n_X^0 \delta n_X \leq -\beta < 0 \quad (137)$$

$$A = -RT \ln \left(1 - \frac{\delta n_X}{n_X^0} \right) > 0 \quad (138)$$

$$\mathcal{L}_s = \frac{A}{T} k_{-4} n_X^0 \delta n_X \geq \beta > 0 \quad (139)$$

Herein too we have $\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_s}{\partial A} = 0$. The gradient of \mathcal{L}_s is obtained as

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_s}{\partial \delta n_X} = k_{-4} n_X^0 \left(R \frac{\delta n_X}{n_X^0 - \delta n_X} - \frac{A}{T} \right) > 0 \text{ and finite} \quad (140)$$

Therefore, the total time derivative of \mathcal{L}_s is given by,

$$\frac{d\mathcal{L}_s}{dt} = \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_s}{\partial \delta n_X} \frac{d(\delta n_X)}{dt} = -(k_{-4} n_X^0)^2 \left(R \frac{\delta n_X}{n_X^0 - \delta n_X} - \frac{A}{T} \right) \delta n_X \leq -\beta' < 0 \quad (141)$$

Again it guarantees the asymptotic stability and the stability under constantly acting small disturbances.

Recall that earlier it was demonstrated¹³ on a generalized footing that all equilibrium states are thermodynamically asymptotically stable and are also stable under the constantly acting small disturbances. Therefore, the preceding demonstrations form the particular examples of the same.

The case of chemical relaxation

When we are analyzing the cases of perturbation of chemically reacting systems one needs to consider the phenomenon of chemical relaxation, which results by the perturbation of its own kind. In laboratory chemical relaxation are studied say by *T*-jump and *p*-jump techniques¹⁹. The main feature that concerns us of these techniques is that the concentration of both the products and reactants get simultaneously perturbed. From the point of view of the study of thermodynamic stability if one uses the partial differential equations describing chemical relaxation then one is ascertaining the stability of the chemical equilibrium towards which the system is approaching. This then becomes yet another case falling within the domain of the preceding section. Whereas if perturbation in the constitutive equations

of chemical relaxation are effected then one is investigating the stability of chemical relaxational process. Both these aspects are analyzed and elaborated in the next two subsections taking the two representative chemical reactions of eqs. (19) and (20).

Thermodynamic stability of an equilibrium state via chemical relaxation :

The generalized constitutive equations derived for chemical relaxational process¹⁹ is

$$\frac{dx_j}{dt} = -\frac{(x_j - x_j^0)}{\tau}, \text{ with } (x_j - x_j^0) = (n_j - n_j^0) \quad (142)$$

where τ is the relaxation time whose expression is determined by the rate constants of the chemical reaction under investigation and baring a few cases by the equilibrium concentration of the reaction partners.

The case of $A \rightleftharpoons X$: In the case of chemical reaction of eq. (19), the constitutive equation for the chemical relaxation reads as

$$\frac{dx_A}{dt} = -\frac{(x_A - x_A^0)}{\tau}, \text{ with } (x_A - x_A^0) = (n_A - n_A^0) \quad (143)$$

and the actual perturbations as

$$(x_A - x_A^0) = (n_A - n_A^0), (x_X - x_X^0) = (n_X - n_X^0) \quad (144)$$

with the stoichiometric requirements reading as

$$(x_A - x_A^0) = -(x_X - x_X^0) \quad (145)$$

The expression for the relaxation time for chemical reaction of eq. (19) reads as

$$\frac{1}{\tau} = k_{-3} + k_3 \quad (146)$$

Thus the constitutive equations read explicitly as

$$\frac{d(n_A - n_A^0)}{dt} = \frac{d(x_A - x_A^0)}{dt} = \frac{d(\xi - \xi^0)}{dt} = \quad (147)$$

$$\frac{d(x_A - x_A^0)}{\tau} = -\frac{d(n_A - n_A^0)}{\tau}$$

$$\frac{d(\delta n_A)}{dt} = -\frac{\delta n_A}{\tau}, \left| \frac{d(\xi - \xi^0)}{dt} \right| = \frac{\delta n_A}{\tau} > 0 \quad (148)$$

The chemical affinity of chemical relaxation is obtained as

$$A = RT \left[\ln \left(1 \pm \delta n_A \frac{1}{n_A^0} \right) - \ln \left(1 \mp \frac{\delta n_A}{n_X^0} \right) \right] \quad (149)$$

which reduces to (in view of the smallness of the perturbation),

$$\frac{A}{T} = \pm R \left(\frac{1}{n_A^0} + \frac{1}{n_X^0} \right) \delta n_A \quad (150)$$

The thermodynamic Lyapunov function \mathcal{L}_s in the present case is identified as

$$\mathcal{L}_s = \left| \frac{A}{T} \right| \left| \frac{d(\xi - \xi^0)}{dt} \right| = R \left(\frac{1}{n_A^0} + \frac{1}{n_X^0} \right) \frac{(\delta n_A)^2}{\tau} > 0 \quad (151)$$

Thus from eq. (151), we find that $\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_s}{\partial A} = 0$ and the gradient of \mathcal{L}_s is obtained as

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_s}{\partial (\delta n_A)} = 2R \left(\frac{1}{n_A^0} + \frac{1}{n_X^0} \right) \frac{\delta n_A}{\tau} > 0 \text{ and finite} \quad (152)$$

Therefore, the total time derivative of \mathcal{L}_s reads as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d\mathcal{L}_s}{dt} &= \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_s}{\partial (\delta n_A)} \frac{d(\delta n_A)}{dt} = \\ &= -2R \left(\frac{1}{n_A^0} + \frac{1}{n_X^0} \right) \left(\frac{\delta n_A}{\tau} \right)^2 \leq -\beta < 0 \quad (153) \end{aligned}$$

The case of $A + X \rightleftharpoons 2X$: In the case of the chemical relaxation of chemical reaction of eq. (20), eqs. (143) – (145), (147) and (148) remain valid as such. The expression for the relaxation time for chemical reaction of eq. (20) reads as¹⁹

$$\frac{1}{\tau} = 2k_{-4}n_X^0 + k_4(n_X^0 - n_A^0) \quad (154)$$

The chemical affinity of chemical relaxation in this case too is given by eqs. (149) and (150). Similarly, the thermodynamic Lyapunov function \mathcal{L}_s in the present case is given by

eq. (151). Thus herein too we find that $\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_s}{\partial A} = 0$. Also the gradient of \mathcal{L}_s is given by eq. (152) and the total time derivative of \mathcal{L}_s is given by eq. (153), but in both the expressions now the τ is given by eq. (154).

Thus the equilibrium states against the perturbation leading to chemical relaxation in the case of both the chemical reactions considered in both these subsections are asymptotically stable and are also stable under the constantly acting such small perturbations.

Thermodynamic stability of the process of chemical relaxation :

In the case of both the chemical reactions of eqs. (19) and (20), the following equations hold good. The constitutive equations of motion on the relaxational trajectory reads as

$$\frac{d(\delta n_A)^0}{dt} = -\frac{(\delta n_A)^0}{\tau}, \left| \frac{d(\xi - \bar{\xi})^0}{dt} \right| = \frac{(\delta n_A)^0}{\tau} > 0 \quad (155)$$

Notice that now $\bar{\xi}$ corresponds to the final equilibrium state. Therefore, if Δ is used to denote the magnitude of perturbation from the relaxational trajectory then for the corresponding perturbed trajectory the constitutive equations are,

$$\frac{d[(\delta n_A)^0 \pm \Delta]}{dt} = -\frac{(\delta n_A)^0 \pm \Delta}{\tau},$$

$$\left| \frac{d[(\xi - \bar{\xi})^0 \pm \Delta_\xi]}{dt} \right| = \frac{(\delta n_A)^0 \pm \Delta}{\tau} > 0 \quad (156)$$

Thus from eqs. (155) and (156) the constitutive equations pertaining to the thermodynamic perturbation space are obtained as

$$\frac{d\Delta}{dt} = -\frac{\Delta}{\tau}, \left| \frac{d\Delta_\xi}{dt} \right| = \frac{\Delta}{\tau} > 0 \quad (157)$$

Similarly, for the chemical affinity in the perturbation space we obtain the following expression in the case of said two chemical reactions,

$$\left| \frac{\Delta_A}{T} \right| = R \left(\frac{1}{n_A^0} + \frac{1}{n_X^0} \right) \Delta > 0 \quad (158)$$

Correspondingly, \mathcal{L}_s in both the cases is given by

$$L_s = \left| \frac{\Delta_A}{T} \right| \left| \frac{d\Delta_\xi}{dt} \right| = R \left(\frac{1}{n_A^0} + \frac{1}{n_X^0} \right) \frac{\Delta^2}{\tau} \geq \beta > 0 \quad (159)$$

Thus from eq. (159) it is evident that in both the cases the local time derivative of \mathcal{L}_s vanishes, that is,

$$\left(\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_s}{\partial t} \right) \Delta$$

The gradient of \mathcal{L}_s in both the cases reads as

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_s}{\partial \Delta} = 2R \left(\frac{1}{n_A^0} + \frac{1}{n_X^0} \right) \frac{\Delta}{\tau} > 0 \text{ and finite} \quad (160)$$

Therefore, the total time derivative of \mathcal{L}_s in both the cases behaves as

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_s}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_s}{\partial \Delta} \frac{d\Delta}{dt} = -2R \left(\frac{1}{n_A^0} + \frac{1}{n_X^0} \right) \left(\frac{\Delta}{\tau} \right)^2 \leq -\beta < 0 \quad (161)$$

The conclusion is that the process of chemical relaxation is asymptotically stable and also stable under the constantly acting small disturbances.

Final remarks

This paper describes in considerable details how the equipment of CTTSIP works in investigation of thermodynamic stability of irreversible processes. To grasp it in finer details we have chosen very elementary model chemical reactions which includes the case of autocatalytic reaction of practical importance and investigated almost all possibilities of perturbations of real trajectories as well as the cases of chemical equilibrium. The regions and constraints under which asymptotic stability and the stability under constantly acting small disturbances would be guaranteed get clearly revealed. It is amusing to learn that in the case of autocatalytic mechanism to guarantee the thermodynamic stability certain conditions are required to be imposed. Also our analysis reveals that the sufficiently small perturbations in mole numbers that is required to produce a significant perturbation from a chemical equilibrium state are relatively large compared to those considered while perturbing an irreversible chemical reaction proceeding at a finite rate. Now it would be of interest to investigate thermodynamic stability of chemical reactions proceeding at finite rates against the perturbations in the mole numbers of the size involved in the case of realistic perturbation of chemical equilibrium. These aspects are under investigation.

Recall that, we have already spelled out previously¹¹⁻¹³ that no theory of thermodynamic stability got evolved prior to CTTSIP in which Lyapunov's direct method has been rigorously followed. Indeed, some attempts were made by earlier workers but they had to resort to certain illfounded propositions (which Lavenda²⁰, Keizer and Fox²¹, Landsberg²² and one of us¹¹⁻¹³ have discussed earlier at length) and the inherent claim is that their theories are tenable in the situations close to equilibrium^{2,3,9,14,20,23,24} and hence no attempt has been made to compare our results with those ones if could be arrived at for the presently investigated cases using any one of the earlier theories. In contrast, it gets lucidly revealed from the above discussion that there is no restriction at all for the application of CTTSIP in terms of whether the system happens to be close to or far away

from equilibrium or whether the process falls in the linear or nonlinear regime (from the thermodynamic or from the constitutive theory point of views). Thus the comprehensive character of CTTSIP thereby gets duly illustrated.

Appendix

The gist of Lyapunov's direct method⁴⁻⁶ of stability of motion is described below (for the convenience of readers) the details of which can be found in standard text books of mathematics including the monographs cited in this paper.

(1) Let the given differential equations of the *perturbed motion* be

$$(A1) \frac{dx_i}{dt} = X_i(t, x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) \quad (i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n)$$

The trivial solution of eq. (A1) is

$$(A2) x_i \equiv 0$$

where x_i 's have been defined as

$$(A3) x_i = |z_i - z_i^0|, x_{i0} = |z_{i0} - z_{i0}^0| = \lambda = \text{small const.}$$

where z_i^0 are the coordinates of the real motion and z_i are those for the corresponding perturbed trajectory. The equations of unperturbed motion then read as

$$(A4) x_i^0 \equiv 0, x_{i0}^0 = 0$$

Thus x_i 's are the small perturbation coordinates in the domain,

$$(A5) t \geq t_0, t_0 \geq 0, x_i \leq H, H > 0$$

where H is a sufficiently small positive constant and

$$(A6) \therefore X_i(t, 0, 0, 0, \dots, 0) = 0$$

(2) Let $V(t, x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n)$ be a *differentiable Lyapunov function* such that,

(i)

$$(A7) V(t, x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n) \geq \epsilon(x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n) > 0$$

$$(A8) \epsilon(0, 0, 0, \dots, 0) = 0, V(t, 0, 0, 0, \dots, 0) = 0$$

That is V has a *strict minima* at the origin and ϵ is a continuous positive number.

(ii) if,

$$(A9) \frac{dV}{dt} = \left(\frac{\partial V}{\partial t} + \sum_i \frac{\partial V}{\partial x_i} X_i \right) \leq 0$$

for $t \geq t_0$, the unperturbed motion is *stable*.

(3) Outside an *arbitrarily small neighbourhood* of the origin if,

$$(A10) \sum_i x_i^2 \geq \delta^2 > 0, t \geq T_0 \geq t_0$$

and in addition to 2(i) [i.e. eqs. (A7) and (A8)] above if we have,

$$(A11) \frac{dV}{dt} \leq -\beta < 0$$

where δ^2 and β are the positive constants, then $x_i \equiv 0$ ($i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$) is *asymptotically stable*.

(4) Further, if,

$$(A12) V > 0, V(t, 0, 0, \dots, 0) \equiv 0, \frac{dV}{dt} \leq -\beta < 0$$

and the derivatives $\partial V / \partial x_i$ are the finite then the *unperturbed motion* is *stable under the constantly acting small disturbances*. This is Malkin's theorem.

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